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Case Report

Deniz Duman Günsay¹, Asena Çiğdem Doğramacı²

1. MD, Defne State Hospital, Hatay, Türkiye, dumandeniz08@gmail.com, 0000-0002-5877-9294
2. Prof. Dr., Mustafa Kemal University, Faculty of Medicine, Dermatology, Hatay, Turkey, Catahan85@yahoo.com, 0000-0003-4986-2149

Corresponding Authors: Dr. Deniz Duman Gürsoy, Defne Devlet Hastanesi, Bostancık, 31000 Defne/Hatay, dumandeniz08@gmail.com

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Acneiform Eruption Due To Erlotinib Treatment: A Case Report

ABSTRACT

Objective: Cutaneous leishmaniasis (CL) is a climate-sensitive disease; changes in temperature, precipitation, and humidity levels can affect sandflies and reservoir hosts by altering their distribution, survival time, and population size. This article elaborates on the diagnostic challenges, treatment process and follow-up of a series of cutaneous leishmaniasis cases.

Cases: This case series comprises a total of six distinct cases of cutaneous leishmaniasis referred to our institution. Three of the individuals were female and four were male. The patients were diagnosed via Polymerase Chain Reaction (PCR), punch biopsy, PAS/EZN staining, and blood smear. Glucantime treatment was initiated in all patients. Our institution has granted ethics committee approval, and informed consent was obtained from all participants.

Conclusion: Although the microorganism responsible for leishmaniasis has been identified for over a century, the disease remains a significant public health concern in many countries, particularly in developing nations. It ranks second in importance after malaria among parasitic diseases due to the difficulty of both treatment and control. In recent years, patients diagnosed with cutaneous leishmaniasis among refugees migrating from Syria to our country have caused an

increase in the disease in our country and affected epidemiological data.

Keywords: *Cutaneous Leishmaniasis, Glucantime, Endemic, Refugees, Protozoan Microorganisms*

Introduction

Leishmaniasis is a disease complex caused by protozoan microorganisms of *Leishmania* and transmitted through the bite of the female sand fly (*midges*). Humans, dogs, and rodents serve as reservoir hosts for various *Leishmania* species, depending on the host's immune response and the specific *Leishmania* species involved. Infection results in cutaneous, mucocutaneous, or visceral disease (1). Although the microorganism responsible for leishmaniasis has been identified for over a century, the disease remains a significant public health concern in many countries, particularly in developing nations. It ranks second in importance after malaria among parasitic diseases due to the difficulty of both treatment and control (2).

The majority of patients cannot benefit from diagnosis and treatment opportunities due to poverty and living in rural areas. Turkey is one of the countries where cutaneous leishmaniasis (*CL*) is endemic. *CL* is still a significant public health problem in the region where Turkey is located, especially in its neighbours such as Iran and Syria. The

refugees who have fled the war in Syria and taken refuge in our country, the number of which exceeds 2 million, pose the risk of many infectious diseases, especially *CL*, being carried to our country (3).

The fact that the lesions are painless, can heal spontaneously without leaving scars in about a year, and do not cause systemic complications or death has led to the acceptance of the disease by society. However, it causes social and psychological problems such as depression, anxiety, and decreased quality of life in those with active lesions or scars. Current treatments for leishmaniasis are far from ideal. Leishmaniasis is one of the most neglected diseases in terms of drug development and discovery. Most of the current antileishmanial drugs are highly toxic, have resistance problems, and require hospitalisation for systemic treatment (4).

The distribution and spread of the disease is related to economic status, behaviour and environmental changes. New settlements, settlements in forest areas, destruction of forests, migration from rural areas to cities, rapid and unplanned urbanization, increase in dog and rodent populations, decrease in insecticide use, increase in the number of immunosuppressed hosts, construction of dams, new irrigation projects, migrations due to various reasons, especially war and natural disasters, play an essential role in the

spread of the disease. It is believed that the population of vector organisms will increase due to the effects of global warming and related climate changes, and their breeding and living areas will expand from sea level to higher altitudes and northern latitudes (5).

CL is a climate-sensitive disease; changes in temperature, precipitation, and humidity levels can affect sandflies and reservoir hosts by altering their distribution, survival time, and population size. The formation of slums in areas where rodent reservoir hosts are densely located as a result of unplanned urbanisation and migration to cities has caused an increase in the incidence of leishmaniasis in these areas (6). This article elaborates on the diagnostic challenges, treatment process and follow-up of a series of cutaneous leishmaniasis cases.

CASES

CASE 1

A 40-year-old female patient applied to our outpatient clinic with a wound on her left hand for 2 months. The patient stated that when the wound on her hand first appeared, it was like a red pimple, and that the wound deepened after using a cream containing the active ingredient nitrofurazone on the wound for 1 month.

The patient lives in the Reyhanlı district of Hatay province. She did not describe any history of fly bites, but stated that she works in the garden seasonally in the spring and fall. No one else in the house

has a similar wound. She has no prior experience in animal husbandry.

In the dermatological examination performed on the patient, there was a 10x4 cm area on the dorsum of the left hand with irregular borders, peripheral erythema, indurated middle, exudative appearance, yellow-white discharge on the edges of the lesion, and a painless, ulcerated lesion on palpation.

The patient was followed up at the external centre in January 2025 with a preliminary diagnosis of pyoderma gangrenosum. When no response was obtained from multiple antibiotics, the patient was referred for further evaluation, potentially for contact dermatitis or pyoderma gangrenosum. A punch biopsy was taken with the preliminary diagnosis of ecthyma gangrenosum—atypical mycobacterial infection. In the histopathology report, Epidermis was not observed in the sections. Mononuclear inflammation extending to the fatty tissue in the dermis; lymphohistiocytic infiltration in the intima of a medium-sized venule and related luminal narrowing, fibrin thrombus in the lumen and sparse, interstitial non-necrotic granuloma are observed.

An ulceration was observed on the dorsum of the left hand, characterised by dermal venous obliteration and lymphohistiocytic infiltration. During the biopsy, epidermis was not observed due to ulceration. Pyoderma gangrenosum (*granulomatous type*) and granulomatous dermatitis, primarily mycobacterial infection, were included in the differential diagnosis. Fungal hyphae/spores were not detected with PAS. No acid-fast bacilli were seen in EZN staining.

Although the current findings were nonspecific, they can also be observed in pyoderma gangrenosum. Although no infectious agent was detected histochemically, the possibility of pyoderma gangrenosum cannot be definitively ruled out at the histopathological level.

Infectious disease was not contagious, and TMP-SMX 800/125 mg was initiated on 02.14.25 with a dosage of 2:1. To exclude the diagnosis of lupus vulgaris, the patient underwent an interferon gamma release test, with a negative result reported.

The diagnosis of leishmania could not be excluded in the patient's current history, and a wound culture and a leishmania smear sample were taken from the ulcerated, discharged lesion on the dorsum of the left hand. There was no growth in the wound culture. Kinetoplasts were observed in the smear, as indicated by the positive polymerase chain reaction (PCR) examination from the lesion, which confirmed the presence of Leishmania.

Figure 1: *Leishmaniasis lesions (A) Before treatment, (B) After treatment*

The patient was admitted to the ward, and intramuscular Glucantime treatment was initiated. The patient weighed 70 kg and received treatment with 12 mL of

Glucantime every 12 hours, consisting of 1.5 ampules in the morning and one ampule in the evening, for 21 days. Daily vital signs, myalgia, and daily ECG monitoring were followed for 3 days, and the patient's blood tests were within normal reference values. No side effects were observed. Mupirocin cream was applied to the ulcerated area within the lesion, mometasone furoate and fusidic acid were applied to the erythematous area at the periphery of the lesion, and the wound dressing was renewed daily. After 21 days of treatment, the patient was discharged with a full recovery, having experienced regression of the lesion.

CASE 2

A 45-year-old male patient applied to our clinic with a complaint of a wound on his right hand for 1 year. The patient reported that the wound on his hand initially resembled a red pimple but had spread and gradually deepened within one year.

The patient lived in the Altınözü district of Hatay province. He did not describe a history of fly bites. No one else in the house has a similar wound. He had no prior experience in animal husbandry. The patient's anamnesis revealed that he regularly does gardening.

In the dermatological examination, there was an ulcerated lesion with irregular borders, widespread erythema on the base, no exudative or purulent discharge, and painless on palpation, in a 5x2 cm area on the dorsum of his right hand.

According to the patient's medical history, the patient was treated with topical nitrofurazone, clobetasol propionate, mupirocin, and sertaconazole nitrate in different centres over the last year for the existing lesion. Since he was unresponsive

to these topicals, systemic terbinafine was started 2 days ago at a dosage of 250 mg/g. All systemic and topical treatments initiated at external centres were discontinued, and native and Leishmania smear samples were taken 1 week later.

The patient was diagnosed with leishmaniasis after the leishmania blood smear result came back positive. It was reported. Intralesional glucantime treatment was initiated once a week. After 10 sessions of intralesional glucantime treatment using the papule formation technique, with lesions treated from the periphery to the centre at 1 cm intervals until the entire lesion turned white, the ulcerated lesion on the right hand regressed.

Figure 2: *The wound on the right hand of the patient*

CASE 3

A 42-year-old male patient applied to our outpatient clinic with a wound on his right cheek for 4 months. The patient stated that the wound on his right cheek started as a pimple-like lesion 4 months ago and gradually deepened in the last 2 months, and turned into its current appearance.

The patient lives in the Altınözü district of Hatay province. He did not describe a history of fly bites. No one else in the house had a similar wound. He had no prior experience in animal husbandry. The patient's anamnesis revealed that he did not do gardening.

In the dermatological examination, there was a 2.5 cm diameter ulcerated lesion with irregular borders and erythema on the right malar region, with widespread erythema and oedema in the periphery, with black-brown crusting, painless on palpation, non-fluctuating, and discharged. Dermoscopy revealed pinpoint haemorrhage foci on globular structures, yellow-black discolouration and crusting containing keratin cysts.

According to the anamnesis taken from the patient, when the ulcerated lesion was applied to an external centre, it was learned that he received systemic cefuroxime axetil 1.5 g per day for 1 week, topical mupirocin and fucidic acid, and intralesional clindamycin treatments, and that he was unresponsive to these treatments.

A wound culture was taken from the patient's ulcerated lesion with discharge. The superficial tissue ultrasonography examined from the current lesion was reported as 'In the superficial B-mode examination of the clinically described region, a loculation area measuring 10x8.5 mm in size, heterogeneous hypoechoic internal structure, which cannot be clearly distinguished from the surrounding tissue and did not show vascular flow coding, was noted.

It was recommended that the patient be evaluated together with clinical and laboratory findings.' A smear sample was

taken from the patient, who used systemic amoxicillin clavulanate 2 g/day for 10 days, with a preliminary diagnosis of leishmania at the control visit 10 days later. A widespread kinetoplast was seen as a result of the smear. The Leishmania smear was positive.

The patient was treated with five sessions of glucantime treatment using the papule formation technique, with 1 cm intervals from the periphery of the lesion to the centre, once a week. This continued until the entire lesion turned white and healed, leaving a 0.3 cm scar.

Figure 3: *The lesion on the right cheek of the patient*

CASE 4

A 60-year-old female patient applied to our outpatient clinic with a wound on her left arm for 1 month. In the dermatological examination, there were five nodular lesions, each 2 cm in diameter, with an erythematous base and yellow crusting in the center on the volar side of the left arm,

and a palpable ulcerated lesion on the dorsum of the left hand, 8x4 cm in diameter, with an erythematous base and widespread black crusting in the center, surrounded by satellite nodules in the periphery.

The patient lives in the Antakya district of Hatay province. She was born in Idlib and has a history of regular visits to Syria. She described a history of fly bites. No one else in the house had similar wounds. There was no history of animal husbandry or gardening.

The patient, who was followed up in internal medicine endocrinology with a known diagnosis of diabetes mellitus and in cardiology with a diagnosis of heart failure, was treated with insulin, captopril, isosorbide dinitrate, atorvastatin, ranolazine, trimetazidine, clopidogrel, dapagliflozin, olmesartan/hydrochlorothiazide, and acetylsalicylic acid treatments.

A leishmania smear was performed with a preliminary diagnosis of Sporotrichoid leishmaniasis due to the patient's history of being in Syria, an endemic region for leishmaniasis. The patient, whose smear blood smear result was positive, was prescribed intralesional 5-glucantime injections and was referred to the Hatay Provincial Health Directorate. The patient stated that he wanted to continue the treatment injections at an external centre. During the control visit, it was observed that the lesions were regressing.

CASE 5

A 54-year-old male patient applied to our outpatient clinic with a wound complaint on his left leg for 1 year. In the dermatological examination, there were

nodular lesions with erythema and ulcerated yellow crusts in the middle of the anterior surface of the left tibia.

The patient lives in the Reyhanlı district of Hatay province. He was a Syrian and had a history of going to and coming from Syria. He described a history of fly bites. Similar wounds were also present in the people he lives with at home. He had no prior experience in animal husbandry. He had no known contact with gardens and no known diseases.

Due to the patient's history of residing in Syria, an endemic region for Leishmaniasis, similar complaints in the family, and the description of fly bites, a Leishmania smear was performed, yielding a preliminary diagnosis of Sporotrichoid leishmaniasis. The patient, whose smear blood smear result was positive, was admitted to the ward, and intramuscular glucantime treatment was started. As a result of the treatment, the patient's lesions healed with scarring.

Figure 4: *Leishmania* lesions on the left leg

CASE 6

A 63-year-old Syrian male patient who lived in the Reyhanlı district of Hatay applied to our outpatient clinic with complaints of wounds on the nose, ears and hands for 3 years. During the dermatological examination, crusted, infiltrative plaques were detected on the patient's nose, ears, and dorsal surfaces of the hands. He did not describe a history of fly bites. No one else in the house had similar wounds. There was no history of animal husbandry, no contact with gardens, and no additional diseases were reported. He did not regularly use any medication. A skin biopsy was performed on the patient with the preliminary diagnoses of pyoderma gangrenosum, atypical mycobacterial infection, sporotrichosis and basal cell carcinoma. Histopathological examination revealed epithelioid granulomas under the stratified squamous epithelium, numerous lymphocytes, plasma cells, and multinucleated giant cell infiltration around these granulomas, as well as basophilic-looking amastigotes with both extracellular and intracellular localisation. These structures stained positively with Giemsa stain.

The patient was diagnosed with leishmaniasis with histopathological examination. The patient was admitted to the ward, and intramuscular glucantime treatment was started. As a result of the treatment, the patient's lesions healed with scarring.

Figure 5: *Leishmania lesions on the nose, ears and hands*

CASE 7

A 46-year-old female patient. She applied to our clinic with a red wound on the front of the ear. In the patient's dermatological examination, an erythematous, asymptomatic plaque was observed on the front of the left ear. She does not describe a history of fly bites. No one else in the house has a similar wound. There was no history of animal husbandry, no garden contact and no additional disease. She did not use any medications regularly.

A biopsy was taken from the patient with the preliminary diagnoses of discoid lupus erythematosus, lupus vulgaris, Bowen's disease, sarcoidosis, squamous cell carcinoma, insect bite, and leishmania. In the histopathological examination,

infiltration consisting of histiocytes, lymphocytes, and plasma cells, as well as granulomas and amastigotes within macrophages, was observed. It stained positive with Giemsa stain.

Figure 6: *Leishmaniasis lesions on the front of the ear*

The patient was diagnosed with leishmaniasis. The patient, who was reported to have leishmaniasis, was treated with five sessions of glucantime treatment using a papule formation technique, with injections at 1 cm intervals from the periphery of the lesion to the centre, administered once a week, intralesionally, until the entire lesion turned white. With the treatment, the patient's lesion healed without scarring..

Discussion

The incidence of CL is closely related to the ecology, climate, and geographic distribution of vectors and reservoirs in the region. Both the host's lifestyle and behavioural patterns, as well as the vector's

reproduction and life characteristics, are essential in CL epidemiology. People infected with the disease, who migrate from endemic to non-endemic regions, can carry it to that region if there are suitable vectors and favourable environmental and climatic conditions. At the same time, uninfected people have a higher risk of infection than the local people when they come to endemic regions. For these reasons, CL epidemics often occur in migrants and non-susceptible individuals who come to endemic regions. There are focal foci of leishmaniasis in most endemic regions. These areas are associated with microecological conditions that affect the vector, parasite, and reservoir host (7). The distribution and spread of the disease are related to economic status, behaviour and environmental changes. New settlements, settlements in forest areas, destruction of forests, migration from rural areas to cities, rapid and unplanned urbanization, increase in dog and rodent populations, decrease in insecticide use, increase in the number of immunosuppressed hosts, construction of dams, new irrigation projects, migrations due to various reasons, especially war and natural disasters, play an essential role in the spread of the disease (8). It is believed that the population of vector organisms will increase due to the effects of global warming and related climate changes, and their

breeding and living areas will expand from sea level to higher altitudes and northern latitudes. CL is a climate-sensitive disease; changes in temperature, precipitation, and humidity rates can affect sandflies and reservoir hosts by altering their distribution, survival time, and population size. The formation of slums in areas where rodent reservoir hosts are densely located as a result of unplanned urbanisation and migration to cities has caused an increase in the incidence of leishmaniasis in these areas (9).

In Turkey, CL is endemic in the Southeastern Anatolia region and the Çukurova region of the Mediterranean region. According to the Ministry of Health's data, approximately half of the 50.381 cases detected throughout the country between 1988 and 2010 were reported from Şanlıurfa province, with 96% of these cases also reported from Şanlıurfa, Adana, Osmaniye, Hatay, Diyarbakır, İçel, and Kahramanmaraş provinces. Şanlıurfa is followed by Adana, Osmaniye, Hatay, Diyarbakır, İçel, Kahramanmaraş, Antalya, Aydın, Kayseri, Niğde, Muş and 47 other provinces that have reported cases (10). In recent years, cases reported from non-endemic regions such as the Western and Northern regions of Turkey consist of refugees from neighbouring countries, especially Syria, and/or people coming from our endemic provinces for

work and education purposes. Although CL is concentrated in certain regions, the long incubation period of the disease and the slow progression of the lesions allow the disease to be detected and diagnosed outside of the areas where it is endemic (11). Due to increased travel to endemic areas and military operations, the number of CL cases has increased in developed countries since the 1990s. Although it is a disease that can occur at all ages, it is more common in children in endemic regions (11, 12).

The characteristics of the host and the parasite determine the formation and healing process of CL. Since leishmaniasis is generally an infection closely related to the immune system, the parasite is often eliminated in many people who acquire it, and clinical infection does not develop. The CL lesion begins as an erythematous papule in areas not covered by clothing, such as the face, neck and extremities, where the infected female sand fly bites. It grows slowly and develops into a nodule or plaque, accompanied by a tightly adherent, crust-covered ulcer in the centre over weeks or months (13). When the hard shell tightly attached to the ulcerated lesion is removed, nail-like protrusions are seen on the underside of the shell, which is called Hulusi Behçet's "nail sign". In the case of multiple bites, there may be various lesions, and these lesions are generally of the same

characteristics. Sporotrichosis-like lesions, characterised by nodular lymphangitis resulting from lymphatic spread, have been described. The lesions are typically painless, unless a secondary bacterial infection occurs. CL caused by *L. tropica* is known as the anthroponotic or dry type and is seen in non-rural areas. The lesions ulcerate slowly and late. There are often multiple, dry, ulcerated nodules and plaques. The lesions typically heal within a year or more, leaving a scar in their place. The incubation period ranges typically from 2 to 8 months (14). CL caused by *L. major* is known as the zoonotic or wet type and is seen in rural areas. It progresses rapidly. The lesions are severely inflamed and ulcerated, typically healing within 2-8 months. Lesions, which are often multiple, may leave large, unsightly, or dysfunctional scars. CL caused by *L. infantum* is seen in the Mediterranean basin. *L. infantum* may also cause visceral leishmaniasis in children (15).

Acute CL lesions usually heal within 1-2 years, leaving a sunken scar. Lesions that persist for more than 2 years are classified as chronic CL. Chronic CL may occur when primary lesions persist for more than 2 years (*Lupoid leishmaniasis*) or when the scar on the healed primary lesion becomes reactivated months or years later (*Residual leishmaniasis*). Anthroponotic, and more rarely zoonotic, CL may develop into lupoid

leishmaniasis, which resembles lupus vulgaris (16). *L. tropica* almost always causes residual CL. Chronic CL may persist for years. The presence of a small number of amastigotes in the lesion may cause a delay in diagnosis. Cutaneous disease may be disseminated (*diffuse CL*), especially in immunosuppressed individuals. This form may be confused with lepromatous leprosy. Mucosal lesions are rare in Old World leishmaniasis, and mucosal dissemination may occur in elderly or immunosuppressed individuals (17).

For the diagnosis of CL, parasitological confirmation is required in patients with a history of living in endemic areas or travelling to endemic regions, as well as clinical findings suggestive of the disease. The material for the smear should be taken from the most recent and active lesion that is not secondarily infected. The diagnosis is confirmed by the observation of amastigotes in microscopic examination of Giemsa-stained smears. Amastigotes are numerous in early lesions, and few in late and secondarily infected lesions. Since amastigotes are very few in chronic cases, they are challenging to detect (18).

In addition, the pressure smear method, acceptable needle aspirate method, culture, incisional skin biopsy, and polymerase chain reaction method are used in diagnosis, performed on biopsy material or samples

sent from skin aspirates. Today, two methods are most commonly used for determining *Leishmania* species: isoenzyme electrophoresis and PCR. Nicolle-Novy-MacNeal (*NNN*) or modified *NNN* media are used for *Leishmania* culture. Positive results are usually obtained from cultures within a week. Under normal conditions, approximately 70% of positive samples show growth. *Leishmania* cannot grow in the presence of bacterial contamination. Therefore, aseptic conditions should be used for culture in media (19). Histopathologically, an inflammatory infiltrate consisting of histiocytes, lymphocytes and plasma cells is seen in the dermis in CL. Amastigotes are found inside and outside the macrophages. Over time, the number of epithelioid cells and giant cells increases, while the number of amastigotes decreases. In chronic lesions, a granulomatous dermatitis pattern is observed. The clinical spectrum of CL is quite broad and can mimic many other skin diseases (20).

CL is not a life-threatening disease that can cause serious problems, and spontaneous recovery is usually observed. Therefore, it is not necessary to treat every patient. The benefits of treatment are that it accelerates recovery, reduces the possibility of recurrence, prevents/reduces scar formation, reduces the risk of disease spread

(*disseminated cutaneous, mucosal*), and reduces the infectious source, especially in anthroponotic CL. The drug or treatment approach to be used in CL should not cause life-threatening complications. Treatment should not be initiated until the disease diagnosis is confirmed. The risk-benefit ratio should be considered for each patient when making a treatment decision. Various treatment methods, including local, systemic, and physical, have been employed in the treatment of CL. The type of parasite, geographic region, and the patient's immunological status affect the effectiveness of the treatment (21). The primary treatment approach in uncomplicated CL cases is local treatment. Wound care and local treatment have been found effective in uncomplicated CL cases, which *L. tropica* and *L. infantum* primarily cause (22). It is essential to keep the lesion clean, as secondary bacterial infection can cause serious complications. The most preferred drugs in CL treatment are pentavalent antimony (*SbV*) compounds. These compounds have been the basis of leishmaniasis treatment since the 1940s (2). The best known pentavalent antimony compounds are: meglumine antimonate (*Glucantime*[®]) and sodium stibogluconate (*Pentostam*[®]) (23). These drugs can be applied intralesionally or systemically. Due to the toxicity risk of systemic treatment

doses, the most preferred method is IL meglumine antimonate treatment. However, if the area of the lesion, the number, size and condition of the lesions are not suitable for IL treatment or if there is no response to IL treatment, systemic treatment can also be applied (24).

The effectiveness of cryotherapy has been reported to range from 53% to 100% in clinical studies. Cryotherapy followed by IL *SbV* local treatment is more effective. In small, non-ulcerated new lesions, cryotherapy can be applied alone. It is recommended to use liquid nitrogen for 15-20 seconds, creating a 1-2 mm ice ring around the lesion, followed by a 20-60 second interval and then another 15-20 seconds of liquid nitrogen. This application can be repeated every three weeks until the healing process is complete. Cryotherapy can cause erythema, oedema, bullae, permanent pigment changes and scarring (25). Thermotherapy can be used as an alternative treatment to cryotherapy in small lesions that are not localised on the eyelids, nose, lips or ears (26).

Clusters of metals in their neutral oxidation states are known as metallic nanoparticles (*NP*) (27). The existence of surface plasmons, which resonate when they interact with electromagnetic radiation to produce a plasmonic band, is a crucial characteristic of this group. The size, shape, and type of

metal used in the nanoparticles all affect the location of the plasmonic band in the electromagnetic spectrum. Targeting both promastigotes and amastigotes versions of *Leishmania* protozoans, metallic nanoparticles have shown promise in antibacterial, anticancer, and antileishmanial properties (28, 29). The elevated levels of reactive oxygen species (*ROS*) are the main factor linked to their mode of action. Rapid surface oxidation is made possible by the high surface-to-volume ratio of metallic nanoparticles (30). Although macrophages produce *ROS* as a defence mechanism, *Leishmania* parasites are usually not killed by the amount of *ROS* produced. 87 By blocking the macrophages' enzymatic pathways, these parasites have evolved defences against oxidative stress. The lattice of the nanoparticle releases metal ions, which increase *ROS* levels within the cell and enhance the efficacy of the parasitocidal activity (31).

The range of nanomaterials covered, including oxides, carbon-based compounds, and metallic nanoparticles, emphasises their potential as potent anti-*Leishmania* treatment agents. The distinct physicochemical characteristics of these nanomaterials—such as their size, shape, chemical composition, and surface charge—

are crucial to their antileishmanial action, as they facilitate membrane penetration and induce cell death. More research into synthesis techniques to alter their surfaces and compositions, however, may result in more effective systems. By surface-functionalizing nanomaterials with biocompatible compounds, for example, the problem of reducing damage to macrophages can be addressed, thereby increasing the selectivity index necessary for optimal treatment (32).

Conclusion

CL affects individuals of all ages and genders, and its incidence increases in situations such as war and natural disasters. Migration due to war and changes in living conditions causes delays in the diagnosis and treatment of the disease, as well as some difficulties in controlling it. In particular, in recent years, patients diagnosed with cutaneous leishmaniasis among refugees migrating from Syria to our country have caused an increase in the disease in our country and affected epidemiological data. Therefore, importance should be given to the necessary health screenings of those entering the country, the implementation of vector control programs and public education on this issue.

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